

LIABILITY ISSUES OF INTERNET PROVIDERS UNDER THE LEGISLATION OF UZBEKISTAN AND OTHER FOREIGN COUNTRIES

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Abstract: In this article, the types of internet providers, their criminal, administrative, and civil liability issues and scopes are analyzed according to the legislation of Uzbekistan and other foreign countries, suggestions are made.

Keywords: *Liability of internet providers, internet providers, ISP, criminal liability, civil liability.*

According to the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, “an Internet provider is a legal entity that provides Internet access services on a commercial basis; cable, broadcast, interactive, IPTV (IP-television), OTT (Over the Top) and online television television (hereinafter referred to as teletext broadcasting) — television programs and other telecommunications using cable television channels that cannot be viewed freely an entity engaged in the distribution and organizational-management process that ensures the production, formation and distribution of its messages in a specific area;”¹. Who are the internet providers in the world and their types, what are their responsibilities? We will touch on these aspects below.

Many people in contemporary culture are served by internet service providers (ISPs). They can also provide software bundles in addition to encoding entries on the internet. The bundles are displayed as

¹ O‘zbekiston Respublikasi axborot texnologiyalari va kommunikatsiyalarini rivojlantirish vazirining buyrug‘i, <https://lex.uz/docs/-4962057?query=internet%20provayder#sr-1>.

browsers, email addresses, and private forums similar to websites (like Google and Yahoo) can be identified as ISPs. They can also create websites for companies. They are all connected to one another via a variety of internet entrance points. The expansion of retail Internet services and dressings contributes to the Internet's rapid commercialization.

This manifestation is also the result of multiple other factors. However, the majority of these ISPs only offered a restricted range of services, and for more extensive coverage, one must connect to regional and national ISPs.

They have the ability to easily detect whatever we have done online. They can simply find out where we are, what device we are using, and which forum we are on. Our data can be borrowed by our assembled profiles, depending on where we are in the world, and sold to third parties without our knowledge for a range of purposes.

We can assume that in order to supply us with more services, the service providers are requesting data about our internet activity. Additionally, it entitles them to view everything we produce online. But things aren't always this way with cases.

The reason why ISPs want to look at our browsing history is clear. Well, there are a few peculiar theories that could apply. Compulsory data retention laws in a few places allow ISPs to search for and record specific customer data that they are legally permitted to keep on file on occasion. This could include, among many other things, the website we visit, our emails, our search and watch histories, the system we use for these tasks, and many more.

Any competent person could quickly figure out every detail of our lives, including browsing history, if a corporation managed to obtain such information. The information may include our bank account information, our purchasing and eating habits, and other personal information like our

marital status, health issues, and even sexual preferences - we don't see any privacy issues here.

ISP negotiates terms of business and money with the marketers and obtains data on their behalf simply because data is correlated with money. The companies then target us by placing relevant adverts on the websites we browse. When children are the targets, this would become much more distressing. Kids usually influence our judgments on family purchases made online, and this data can be very useful for marketers. VPN is used by many people. By means of By using this, people from many states can easily visit the unlimited we site wherever possible there are a huge number of people who can't do that.

ISP can also obtain information by stealing it data if they want it. Some listings are banned by the government from specific web pages different reasons. For example, the government can limit the sites where hate can be expressed that may contain bad words or motivate actions that conflict with a specific theology, including illegal site such as porn or gambling.

Certain states or territories may be prevented from doing so. In this case, ISP is called in by the government to carry out this censorship. Since then, ISP has developed the right to access the sites we explore and it is they who grant us access

They have surveillance to prevent access to those locations, as required by the government.

There are types of internet providers based on methods and tools and they are as follows:

- **Dial-up.** Dial-up is an internet connection from an ISP which is generated via a cable connection on a conventional fixed line. This type of internet connection at the slowest speed, which is around 56 kbps. Users must have a fixed line to be able to obtain a connection compared. The internet

connection which is integrated into the fixed line makes dial-up unusable when the user performs telephone activities.

- **DSL (DIGITAL SUBSCRIBER CONNECTION).** DSL is a type of Internet connection provided by ISPs over landlines using a broadband network with speeds higher than dial-up, ranging from 200 Kbps to 8 Mbps. Note that broadband networks can transmit Internet connections over copper and fiber optic cable connections. Broadband networks can also transmit Internet connections wirelessly, which is commonly used for cellular networks. Wired networking is typically used to connect a broadband network's Internet connection to a device providing an Internet connection such as a modem or router. For DSL, the internet connection is connected via a copper cable network that is used with landlines. However, because the cable runs via a modem, users do not need to have a landline.
- **CABLE TV.** Cable TV is a type of Internet connection that comes from connecting to cable TV. Then the cable television connection, just like DSL, also uses a broadband network. Broadband cable television networks are usually provided via fiber optic cable networks. The cable is then connected to the modem or router to distribute the Internet connection across the device. The Internet connection via a cable TV connection is more stable than DSL, which uses copper cable. The speed of the Internet connection via a cable TV connection can be more than 8 Mbit/s. Then users don't have to have cable TV to use an internet connection. As long as they are in a position that is at hand of a cable TV connection, users can use this type of connection to access the Internet.

- **Satellite connection.** In addition, there are types of ISPs that use spatial communication satellites with broadband networks to provide the internet. To be able to capture a broadband network from a satellite connection, users need a satellite dish. Subsequently, the satellite dish will spread the internet connection to different devices. The internet connection range can be wider than the cable network. However, the use of satellite connections to access the Internet in Uzbekistan is still rare.
- **Mobile Internet Network.** The mobile internet networks, such as 4G or 5G, are the type of internet connection that is often used on cell phones. This type of ISP generates an Internet connection via the cellular network connects via the cellular network to generate internet connection. In order to access an internet connection via a 4G or 5G network, users must have an Internet data package provided by ISP. With this data package, users do not need a cable connection to access the Internet. There are therefore different types of ISPs that are based on your Internet connection services that can be used to access the Internet. However, these ISP services cannot be used directly to access the Internet without subscription registration.

The last type of internet providers is widespread in Uzbekistan and according to 2022 data: “Uzbekistan ranks 89th in the home Internet speed ranking, and its average speed is 49.8 Mbit/s. Over the year, this figure increased by 17.5 Mbit/s, which is the fastest growth rate in Central Asia”². And the most popular internet providers are: Turon Telecom, Sarkor, Uztelecom, TPS, ComNet.

If we focus on the issue of responsibility of internet providers under the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the liability of internet providers is directly stated once time in *the Criminal Code, Article 278* of the Criminal Code,

² <https://repost.uz/internet-provayderi>.

Organization of gambling and other games based on risk in the 4th part of conducting: “provision of services by providers of telecommunication networks, including the Internet global information network, for the organization or conduct of gambling and other games based on risk, copying of relevant software increase, its reproduction, distribution, if it is committed after the application of an administrative penalty for such actions, a fine in the amount of fifty to seventy-five times the amount of the basic calculation, or three hundred to three hundred sixty hours of compulsory community service, or up to three years punishable by correctional work”³.

In addition, in place 1, **part 3 of Article 191 of the Code of Administrative Responsibility**: “Organization or conduct of gambling and other games based on risk in telecommunication networks, including the Internet global information network provision of services or assistance in provision of services by i providers, copying, reproduction, distribution of relevant software -

by confiscating computers and other auxiliary equipment, as well as the money bet on the game and the winnings in the game, objects and other valuable items, citizens from five to ten times the amount of the basic calculation, and officials from ten times to ten times will cause a fine of up to five times”⁴ is cited as.

The above two administrative and criminal responsibilities are given for the same type of action, that is, in actions such as distribution and copying of games related to gambling and risk. However, there may be many other acts or omissions committed by Internet service providers, not only this act of crime or socially dangerous act. For example, there may be content related to religious extremism or violence.

³ the Criminal Code of Republic of Uzbekistan, <https://lex.uz/docs/-111453>.

⁴ the Code of Administrative Responsibility of Republic of Uzbekistan, <https://lex.uz/docs/-97664>.

Moreover, the scope of liability is not limited to criminal and administrative liability, but also includes civil and economic liability.

According to the civil code, the responsibility and obligations of internet providers are not clearly stated, but internet providers are considered providers, i.e. legal entities that provide services, so they have obligations to the service providers, and if internet providers provide contractual services if he does not show it or if he does not perform it well, this inaction may cause civil liability. A similar situation implies economic responsibility in the case of contractual relations with a legal entity or business entities, an individual entrepreneur.

As follows in ***the Civil code, Article 1018***: “Persons responsible for damage caused by defects of goods, work, service The damage caused due to product defects shall be compensated by the seller or manufacturer of the product at the choice of the victim. The damage caused by the defect of the work (service) must be compensated by the person (executor) who performed the work or provided the service. Damage caused by failure to provide complete or reliable information about goods (work, service) shall be compensated in accordance with the provisions of this article”⁵.

That is, in this situation, if, as a result of the low-quality service provided by the Internet provider, property damage is caused to legal entities or individuals, the Internet providers may be held civilly or economically liable.

Below we analyze the liability issues of internet providers in some countries:

For example, ***in Japan*** “EC rules, which apply the same horizontal approach as the Japanese bill, provide for the limitation of not only civil liability but also criminal liability. The latest Japanese bill limits liability of damages caused by copyright infringement, defamation, and other rights infringements”⁶. Accordingly, in 2000s,

⁵ O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Fuqarolik kodeksi, <https://lex.uz/docs/-180552#-196893>.

⁶ https://www.softic.or.jp/symposium/open_materials/10th/en/hagiwara1-en.pdf.

Japan developed a separate law on ISP liability, with some models taken from EC and US legislation. According to the draft law, in cases of infringement of copyright, defamation and other violations of rights, Internet providers will be held criminally or civilly liable, depending on the subjects, if they received a warning or had information, but did not take action.

In the United States, the Digital Millennium Copyright Act of 1998 establishes Internet service providers' accountability for copyright infringement and websites. It offers a way to get the illegal content taken down from the websites. An authorized agent and registration with the US Copyright Office are prerequisites. Additionally, they mandate that the site operator must have known about the content that was infringed upon in order to be held accountable.

Europe has two alternative approaches: the vertical method, which was adopted in the US, applies various liability regimes to different sections of the law. Another is vertical, in which the same liability applies regardless of the form of infringement. Specific liability exclusions are provided by directives.

In Uzbekistan, there is no law on ***the scope*** of liability of Internet providers, even in the codes on criminal and administrative responsibility, there are no specific cases, limits, and comments on their responsibility.

The government should make some stringent laws regarding this because it contains a large amount of data including the personal information also, so it's necessary to save from any kind of infringement.

From the above, we can come to the following general conclusions:

- According to the legislation of Uzbekistan, a legal document defining the scope of responsibility of internet providers should be developed.

- Criminal liability of Internet providers should be included in the criminal code when they act to violate copyright or other rights granted to them.
- The concept of secondary liability of Internet providers and in what cases it occurs should be legally reflected in the code and the law of Uzbekistan.

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